

THERMAL REGULATION OF VASCULARIZED POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR ENHANCED THERMOMECHANICAL PERFORMANCE

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Keywords: Thermomechanical, Microvascular, Thermal Regulation

ABSTRACT

Fires or other causes of unexpected increases in temperature cause polymer matrix composites (PMC) to fail under mechanical loads easily sustained at room temperature. However, heat can be removed and temperature reduced in PMCs by active cooling through an internal vascular network. During active cooling, fluid is pumped through the channels to transfer heat from the PMC to the fluid. Here we examine the ability of active cooling to enhance mechanical performance and survivability of PMCs under thermomechanical loading. Channels are manufactured into structural PMCs (*i.e.* carbon fiber/epoxy and glass fiber/epoxy) using the Vaporization of Sacrificial Components (VaSC) technique. During VaSC, a sacrificial template of the intended vascular network is embedded into the fiber preform prior to matrix curing, then removed at elevated temperatures to create a hollow vasculature. Two testing protocols are used to compare non-cooled and actively cooled PMCs under thermomechanical loading. In the first, a flexure test is conducted in a convective environment with temperatures above the glass transition temperature of the composite to compare retention of flexural modulus in the high temperature environment vs. at room temperature. In the second test, the time-to-failure of PMCs under sustained compressive load and one-sided radiant heating is measured. Results demonstrate the dramatic improvement in PMC performance under thermomechanical loading afforded by active cooling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites possess outstanding structural properties at room temperature, including high strength, high stiffness, low density, and excellent fatigue life. However, the service temperature for fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites is severely limited by the relatively low glass transition temperature (T_g) of typical matrix materials, including epoxy (*ca.* < 200 °C), vinyl ester (*ca.* < 150 °C), and even bismaleimides and polyimides (*ca.* < 250 °C) [1]. Above T_g , the structural performance of the PMC is greatly reduced as a result of matrix softening. In addition, damage may form in PMCs after only short exposure to high temperature including delamination, matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding, and even combustion and fire [2]. Application of PMCs in high heat conditions requires a method for thermal regulation. An internal vascular network provides a

platform for thermal regulation by allowing for circulation of a cooling fluid to remove heat and reduce temperature. The active cooling concept is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the concept for active cooling of PMCs. When fluid is pumped through internal vascular channels, heat is transferred from the solid to the fluid. Removing heat from the solid material reduces its temperature and in turn improves the material's structural performance under thermal load.

Kozola *et al.* [3] evaluated active cooling in an epoxy cooling fin heated at the base. Active cooling increased the effective heat transfer coefficient 53-fold compared to without cooling. This increase in heat transfer coefficient reduced the mean field temperature in the area of the cooling network from 60 °C to 30 °C. Phillips *et al.* [4] evaluated heat load and effective heat transfer coefficient in an actively heated fin subject to free convective cooling using thermography. An analytical model of the temperature field was developed. Soghrati *et al.* [5,6] modeled actively cooled PMCs subject to constant heat flux on one surface. The effect of channel spacing, channel shape, coolant type, flow rate, applied thermal load, and top surface boundary condition were evaluated. Experiments were used to confirm the accuracy of the model.

This paper discusses results from tests used to assess the performance enhancement afforded by active cooling to PMCs under thermomechanical loading. First, the VaSC method for manufacturing vascular networks is discussed. Next, results from two separate tests assessing thermomechanical performance of active cooled PMCs are presented. The paper then finishes with a brief summary and a discussion of future areas of interest.

2 VASCULAR NETWORK MANUFACTURE BY VASC

The VaSC procedure was first developed by Esser-Kahn *et al.* [7] and Dong *et al.* [8] and is used for manufacture of vascular networks in this study. Sacrificial fibers (SF) composed of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) treated with catalyst (*e.g.* tin(II) oxalate or tin(II) octoate) are integrated into a fiber preform prior to matrix solidification. The catalyst lowers the degradation temperature of the PLA while allowing the SF to survive typical PMC manufacturing processes up to 177 °C. It can then be removed during a 200 °C post-cure in a vacuum environment to create a hollow channel. SFs can be integrated directly into the textile manufacturing process to create complex, three-dimensional network architectures. In addition, the sacrificial material is a thermoplastic polymer and can be formed into complex shapes through melt or solvent processing. Vascular architectures have been created from laser cut hot pressed sheets, sintered spheres, electrospun fibers, and 3D printed templates [9].

3 RETENTION OF STIFFNESS

Flexural modulus of an actively cooled PMC in a high temperature environment was evaluated. A four-point bending test (ASTM D7264) was performed in a convectively heated environmental chamber while water was pumped through the channels at a fixed flow rate. This test is shown schematically in Figure 2a. The composites were composed of a 3D orthogonally woven glass fiber textile infused with EPON 862/EPIKURE W (100:26.4 by wt.) using vacuum assisted resin transfer molding and cured at 121 °C for 8 hours (Figure 2). Channels were manufactured using VaSC. The

actively cooled composite contained 8 channels, which were placed near the top and bottom surfaces to increase cooling performance. Non-cooled controls used the same fiber textile but did not contain channels. Flexural modulus was compared with and without cooling. Retained flexural modulus (RFM) was defined as the modulus at a given environmental temperature divided by the modulus at room temperature.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic of thermomechanical testing setup for actively cooled composites. (b) Schematic of the unit cell of the actively cooled composite (channel volume fraction = 3.0%), showing the sacrificial fibers in red, the warp tows are shown in green, the weft tows in yellow, and the z-tows in blue. The areal density of the fabric is 4.07 kg/m². In the warp layers there are 3.0 tows/cm, whereas in the weft layers there are 2.7 tows/cm.

Active cooling of PMCs leads to vastly improved mechanical performance at high temperature (Figure 3). For actively cooled specimens, nearly 90% retention of flexural modulus is achieved at 325 °C environmental temperature with a total coolant flow rate of 160 ml/min. In stark contrast, control specimens possess no structural capacity at the same temperature and show a sharp drop in flexural modulus when the environmental temperature approaches the T_g of the matrix (150 °C by dynamic mechanical analysis). Actively cooled composites show no such drop in properties near T_g and only a modest decrease in flexural modulus over the range of temperatures tested.

Figure 3: RFM of actively cooled (160 ml/min total flow rate) and non-cooled control specimens as a function of environmental temperature. Results represent an average of three tests with error bars equal to one standard deviation.

4 ENHANCED SURVIVABILITY

Survivability of actively cooled PMCs under sustained thermomechanical loading was evaluated using the test setup shown schematically in Figure 4. Survivability is assessed by measuring time-to-failure under constant compression and one-sided radiant heating. The temperature on the non-heated face was monitored using an IR camera. Coolant was pumped through straight, parallel channels oriented perpendicular to the loading axis in actively cooled composites. The composites were manufactured from IM7/977-3 prepreg (donated by Boeing) using the layup shown in Figure 5a. Six evenly spaced channels were manufactured in active cooled composites using the VaSC method. Figure 5b shows an image of a channel in the composite following manufacture. During testing, 200 MPa compressive load was applied to the top and bottom edges of the sample. Then, a uniform heat flux was applied to one face and time-to-failure was measured. Specimens that survived for more than 30 minutes were recorded as “did not fail” (DNF), and the test was ended.

Figure 4: Schematic of the test setup used to compare time-to-failure under sustained thermomechanical loading with and without active cooling.

Figure 5: Manufacturing of vascularized PMC samples. a) Sacrificial fibers were incorporated in the $[0/90]_{4s}$ layup by cutting the central $[90]_2$ ply along the direction of the carbon fibers. This created a sufficiently large space to incorporate the sacrificial fiber without distorting the orientation of the surrounding 0° plies. 340 μm diameter sacrificial fibers were used to match the thickness of two plies.

b) An image from optical microscopy of a 340 μm diameter channel in the carbon/epoxy sample following VaSC.

Results from survivability testing are shown in Table 1. The actively cooled composite survived for more than 30 minutes at heat flux as high as 50 kW/m². Above that, time to failure decreased with increased heat flux. In contrast, the non-cooled composite failed in about 1 minute at 30 kW/m². The heat flux had to be reduced to 5 kW/m² before the non-cooled composite survived for 30 minutes.

	Supplied Heat Flux [kW/m ²]	Time-To-Failure [s]
Non-Cooled Composite	5	DNF
	10	592
	15	218
	20	144
	20	89
Actively Cooled Composite	50	DNF
	55	893
	60	269
	65	174
	70	105

Table 1: Time-to-failure for non-cooled and actively cooled composites under 200 MPa compressive load as a function of heat flux. Total flow rate of water through the channels in actively cooled composites was 90 ml/min, evenly distributed among the channels. If the specimen survived for more than 30 minutes, the test was ended and the result was recorded as “DNF”.

5 SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

Active cooling has been shown to greatly enhance the structural performance of actively cooled composites under thermomechanical loading. Two testing protocols were developed and used to evaluate thermomechanical performance. In the first protocol, the stiffness of actively cooled composites was compared to non-cooled composites in a high temperature environment. In the second protocol, the survivability of actively cooled composites was compared to non-cooled composites by measuring time-to-failure under sustained compressive load and one-sided radiant heating. In both cases, results showed tremendous improvement to structural performance as a result of active cooling. Future work should be directed at applying the active cooling approach to real world applications. Past studies and the present work have demonstrated the effectiveness of active cooling. With the newly developed VaSC method, active cooling is simple to implement on the materials side. Further research must be done to examine how an actively cooled composite can interface with existing structural systems, such as aircraft, particularly in terms of the required pumping power and heat removal from the coolant to allow for recirculation. Furthermore, before application in real world systems is possible, the damage tolerance of the active cooling network must be known. If the network is blocked or damaged, circulation of the coolant may be interrupted, potentially resulting in structural failure of the material. Redundant networks based on the venation in leaves could be an approach to avoid this dangerous scenario.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research as part of a Multidisciplinary University Research Initiative, Award No. FA9550-09-1-0686, *Synthesis, Characterization and Prognostic Modeling of Functionally Graded Hybrid Composites for Extreme Environments*. Financial support was also provided by the National Science Foundation

Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant No. DGE 11-44245. The authors thank Boeing for donating prepreg material and CU Aerospace for assistance with manufacturing the sacrificial fibers used in this study.

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